

EFFECT OF CNTs CONTENT AS TERTIARY FILLER ON CNTs/xGNP/SG/EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES ON THE THROUGH- PLANE CONDUCTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have the potential to be used as the third conductive filler due to nano-sized and tube-shaped, so as to fill the gap between the second conductive filler which is larger in size. However, the nano size of CNTs will function effectively if properly dispersed in matrix polymers. Therefore, a high-speed mechanical mixer (RW20-KIKA-WERK) and an internal mixer (Haake Reomix) were used to produce a good mixture of nanocomposites. The mixture of CNTs/xGNP/SG/epoxy is poured into a steel molds and continued with a fabrication process using a hot press machine for 1.5 hours, at a pressure of 12 MPa, and a temperature of 150°C. The results showed that the highest through-plane conductivity was obtained in the composition of 6 wt.% of CNTs, which was 41 S/cm. Furthermore, the optimization was carried out to the composition of the maximum through-plane conductivity (6 wt.%). The optimization molding parameters, using Taguchi method L9 (3³) orthogonal array is able to increase the through-plane conductivity as 41.46%, using the optimum parameters of M_r 3 = 150 °C, M_p 1 = 8 MPa, and M_t 1 = 60 minutes become 58 S/cm. This condition can be achieved because the third filler of CNTs can be dispersed well at the optimum parameters.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have the potential to be used as conductive fillers to improve the electrical conductivity and mechanical properties of conductive polymer composite materials. This is because CNTs have a high surface area and electrical conductivity [1, 2]. However, the nano size of CNTs is a challenge for researchers because this material is easy to agglomerate, lower the electrical conductivity and mechanical properties of the resulting composite [1, 2]. The researchers have made some efforts to improve the electrical conductivity by using conductive filler such as graphite [3-5], graphine [6-10], CNTs [11-13], Carbon fiber [14, 15], and expanded graphite [16, 18]. However, not many of these studies were investigated uses through-plane electrical conductivity.

Heizel *et al.* [19] focused his study on low cost bipolar plates for polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM) Fuel Cells. Suherman *et al.* [20] using carbon nanotubes (CNTs) as the secondary conductive filler to produce nanocomposites using a compression molding, through optimizing molding parameters such as molding pressure, molding temperature, and molding time. They found that the synergistic effect between CNTs as the second filler and synthetic graphite as the main filler was able to obtain the best electrical conductivity value on bipolar plate material. Several optimization methods have also been used to obtain the desired properties of the material produced. Taguci is a quite often used method to optimize process parameters, because this method can reduce the number of experiments to obtain optimal conditions, so as reduce the cost and time required [20, 21]. Liu *et al.*

[21]; Asiltürk & Akkus [22]; Akyalcin *et al.* [23]; Yıldırım [24] have conducted research to optimize manufacturing processes using Taguchi Method. They found that Taguchi Method was able to get the optimum value of the optimized parameter.

In this study, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) were used as tertiary fillers. Two grade types of graphene platelets (xGNP): M and C grade were used as the secondary; and Synthetic Graphite (SG) as a main conductive filler. Through-plane conductivity and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) were investigated on the fracture surface of the specimen. To obtain the optimal through-plane conductivity from the nanocomposite material produced, the Taguchi method was used.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Three conductive fillers with different particle shapes and sizes were used in this study. Synthetic graphite (SG) with the largest particle size of 74 μm and flake shape used as the main filler. Graphene nanoplatelets (xGNP) and carbon nanotubes (CNTs) which have micron and nano sizes are used as the second and third conductive fillers. The materials used were obtained from Asbury Carbons Inc., US for SG materials, XG Science, Inc., USA for xGNP and US Composites for low epoxy resin viscosity (6 poise).

2.2 Preparation of nanocomposites

The Mixing process of xGNP/SG in the epoxy was through three stages. In the first stage, a ball mill was used to mix xGNP and SG at different wt.% to get the homogenous mixture. The weight ratio of stainless steel balls (10 mm in diameter) and powder used was 4: 1, which were mixed at 200 rpm for 1 hour. Epoxy and curing agent are then mixed using a mechanical mixer in the second stage (RW20-KIKA-WERK) at 1200 rpm for 40s. In the last stage, the xGNP, SG, and epoxy were mixed using an internal mixer (Haake Reomix) at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Rotational speed and rotation times are constant at 25 rpm and 10 minutes in all mixing processes. Then, the mixtures of CNTs/xGNP/SG/epoxy nanocomposites were poured at molding temperatures of 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, molding pressures of 30 MPa, and molding time of 1.5 h into a steel mold.

2.3 Selection of control factor

The Taguchi method is used to obtain the optimal experimental results by minimizing the number of experiments performed, through orthogonal array of L9 (3^3). Three main parameters used in this study; molding temperature (M_t) = 110, 130, 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, molding pressure (M_p) = 8, 10, 12 MPa, and molding time (M_i) = 60, 75, 90 minutes.

2.4 Characterization of nanocomposites

The through-plane conductivity of the CNTs/xGNP/SG/Epoxy nanocomposites was measured using a through-plane conductivity tester, manufactured by Zentrum für Brennstoffzellen Technik in Duisburg, Germany. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to identify the conductive fillers dispersion within polymer matrix on fracture surfaces of CNTs/xGNP/SG/Epoxy nanocomposites.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effect of CNTs content on the through-plane conductivity

The through-plane conductivities of CNTs/xGNP/SG/epoxy nanocomposites with CNTs addition at different loading concentration show in Figure 1. Figure.1 shows that addition of M grade xGNP from 3 wt.% (26 S/cm) to 6 wt.%, (41 S/cm) increase the through plane conductivity sharply (57.7%), but 9% addition of M grade xGNP slightly reduced through plane conductivity of the composite produced (40 S/cm). Figure.1 also shows that addition of C grade xGNP from 3 wt.% (32 S/cm) to 6 wt.% (33 S/cm) slightly increase the through plane conductivity of the nanocomposites produced. However,

there was a drastic decline in through plane conductivity at 9 wt.% addition. Overall, two types xGNP addition from 3 to 6 wt.% are able to increase the through-plane conductivity conductivity of the resulting composite, but 9 wt.% addition apparently decreases the through plane conductivity in both types of xGNP. The decreasing of through plane electrical conductivity is caused by high nanostructured CNTs tend to agglomerate [1, 2, 12]. The highest through-plane conductivities was achieved at 6 wt.% CNTs for both M grade and C grade xGNP.

Figure 1: CNTs content on the through-plane conductivity of nanocomposites

3.2 Optimization of molding process parameters of CNTs/xGNP/SG/epoxy nanocomposites

To improve through-plan conductivity, the molding parameters of CNTs/xGNP/SG/epoxy nanocomposites were carried out on compositions with the highest through-plan conductivity (41 S/cm), which used M grade xGNP as the second filler, and 6 wt.% CNTs as the third filler. Three molding parameters such as molding pressure, molding time, and molding temperature were used in the optimization process. The through-plane conductivity using the Taguchi method L9 (3^3) orthogonal array with 3 levels control factor are shown in Table 1.

Run	M_{tr} ($^{\circ}$ C)	M_p (MPa)	M_t (minutes)	Through-plane conductivity (S/cm)
1	110	8	60	50
2	110	10	75	33
3	110	12	90	40
4	130	8	75	47
5	130	10	90	46
6	130	12	60	42
7	150	8	90	47
8	150	10	60	51
9	150	12	75	43

Table 1: Molding parameters process using L9 (3^3) orthogonal array with 3 level control factor, where M_{tr} : Molding temperature, M_p : Molding pressure, and M_t : Molding time

Table 1. Shows that each molding parameter used produces different through-plane conductivity. This shows that the molding parameters used affect the through plane conductivity obtained [25-27]. Before the optimization was carried out, the through-plane conductivity obtained was 41 S/cm. However, after optimization using Taguchi array L9 (3^3) on CNTs/xGNP/SG/epoxy nanocomposites material was conducted, the highest through-plane conductivity obtained was 51 S/cm at run 8. Thus, the increase in through-plane conductivity of CNTs/xGNP/SG/epoxy nanocomposites produced is 24.4%. The effect of molding parameters in producing CNTs/xGNP/SG/epoxy nanocomposites material based on SN ratios is shown in Figure 2. Figure 2 shows the optimal combination based on SN ratios (Larger is better) for the predetermined parameters, namely molding temperature ($M_{tr}3 =$

150 °C), molding pressure ($M_{p1} = 8$ MPa), and molding time ($M_{t1} = 60$ minutes). Run 10 at parameters M_{tr} 3, M_{p1} and M_{t1} is carried out further to obtain the optimal through-plane conductivity of CNTs / xGNP / SG / epoxy nanocomposites.

Table 2. Shows through-plane conductivity obtained based on the taguchi L9 (3^3) orthogonal array recommendation. The recommended through-plane conductivity Taguchi reaches 58 S/cm, increased by 16% compared to the initial run, which was 50 S/cm. This increase is caused by CNTs as the third filler can be dispersed well and no agglomeration occurs [2, 11].

Figure 2: Effect of molding parameters for S/N ratios

No		Through-plane conductivity
1	The initial (run 1)	50 S/cm
2	Taguchi recommendation (based on SN ratios (run 10))	58 S/cm

Table 2: Through plane conductivity of nanocomposites

Figure 3: SEM fracture surface of CNTs/xGNP/SG/epoxy nanocomposites (a) Initial run (run 1), and (b) Taguchi recommendation (run 10).

In figure 3a. Initial run (run 1) shows that the third conductive filler of CNTs agglomerate in most areas, while in Taguchi recommendations (run 10), CNTs are well dispersed and agglomeration do not show on the matrix, even though CNTs that have nanosize sizes tend to agglomerate (see figure 3.b). This is why the through-plane conductivity obtained (run 10) could increase to 58 S/m.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Research on carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in producing CNTs/xGNP/SG/epoxy nanocomposites and optimizing molding parameters using the Taguchi method has been carried out. Some conclusions of this study are as follows.

1. The use of CNTs as the third filler in CNTs/xGNP/SG/epoxy nanocomposites had been succeeded to increase the through-plane conductivity at a composition of 6 wt.% for both types of graphene used (M and C grade).
2. Optimizing the molding parameters using the Taguchi method is able to increase the through-plane conductivity of CNTs/xGNP/SG/epoxy nanocomposites produced as 41.46%.

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